

Right to Equality in Indian Constitution: Provisions, Significance and Landmark cases

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Abstract: *The paper will analysis on the Provisions, Significance and Landmark cases in relation with Right to Equality (Articles 14–18) in Indian Constitution. Qualitative data analysis is used as a tool. Furthermore, the article will clearly analysis insight view of the Equality before Law and Equal Protection of Laws, Prohibition of Discrimination, Equality of Opportunity, Abolition of Untouchability, Abolition of Titles. A fundamental principle of democratic society is the Right to Equality, which is protected by Articles 14 to 18 of the Indian Constitution. This right prohibits discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, or place of birth, guaranteeing that everyone is treated equally before the law. In conclusion the paper will also focus the landmark cases and significance.*

Keywords: *Rights, Equality, Indian, Constitution, caste*

Introduction

Part III (Articles 12–35) of the Indian Constitution enshrined "*Fundamental Rights*" also Known as the "*Magna Carta of Indian Constitution*" (Vajiram, 2026), they are divided into six categories: the Right to Freedom (Articles 19–22), the Right to Equality (Articles 14–18), the Right to Freedom of Religion (Articles 25–28), the Right to Cultural and Educational Rights (Articles 29–30), and the Right to Constitutional Remedies (Article 32). the Indian judiciary guards' fundamental rights when executive and legislative activities violate these rights, Additionally, the "*Conscience of the Constitution*" refers to the fundamental rights (Vajiram, 2026). The right to equality ensures that everyone is treated equally before the law, prohibits on public place, treats everyone equally in public place, and strictly prohibition of untouchability. Justice and fairness of Indian society is found in the specific provisions relating to the Right to Equality included in Articles 14 to 18 of the Constitution. The Indian Constitution guarantee that no one is subjected to discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth, gender, etc., and that everyone is treated equally before the law and given equal opportunity to all (NEXT IAS, 2025).

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Objectives

The objective of the study is to examining the Provisions, Significance and Landmark cases Right to Equality (Articles 14–18) in Indian Constitution.

Methodology

Using secondary data analysis from news, scholarly works and other related documents in relation with the Right to Equality (Articles 14–18) in Indian Constitution. Furthermore, qualitative methodology of research employs for study.

Provisions in Indian Constitution

All citizen of India, regardless of their religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth, gender, etc are guaranteed equal rights. The provisions listed below are in accordance with the Indian Constitution in relation with the provisions of (Articles 14–18) that are Rights to Equality (Khaskalam, 2025).

- ***Equality before Law and Equal Protection of Laws (Article 14):*** Equality before the law or equal protection under the law is guarantee to all in the Indian soil. This privilege includes all Indian citizens, foreign nationals, and legal entities like corporations, etc. And it is influence by the British notion of "Equality before Law" and the American Constitution's idea of "Equal Protection of Laws." According to the Supreme Court, the "Rule of Law," cannot be abolish by a constitutional amendment which is inserted in Article 14 of the Indian Constitution, because it is a "basic feature" of the document. Under Article 361, the President of India and State Governors are granted special privileges.
- ***Prohibition of Discrimination (Article 15):*** According to Article 15, the state is prohibited from discriminating against any citizen based on their race, religion, caste, sex, or place of birth, etc. All citizens of India are allowed to access in public place without limitation, disability, etc. The state government has the power to implement programme for the advancement of scheduled castes, or scheduled tribes, for women, children, economic backwards and weaker section and the state has the authority to implement reservation of seats in educational institutions for economically disadvantaged segments of society.

- ***Equality of Opportunity in Public Employment (Article 16)***: Equal employment and appointment opportunities to all citizens guarantees under the Indian Constitution's Article 16. Citizens cannot be subjected to discrimination on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, descent, place of birth, or place of residence, etc. Permanent residential certificate is required for some jobs. The state government has the power to reserve position and appointment on government jobs and the 103rd Amendment Act of 2019 added reservation up to 10% of appointments for economically weaker group like family income or other measures of economic disadvantages.
- ***Abolition of Untouchability (Article 17)***: Article 17 of the Indian Constitution prohibits the practice of "untouchability" in any form and has eliminated it. Infirmity due to untouchability by any action are considered as a crime and will be punished by law. In Indian history the term "untouchability" describes societal limitations placed on specific groups of people according to their caste of birth and untouchability is strongly against by Dr. Ambedkar the drafting committee chairman of Indian constitution.
- ***Abolition of Titles (Article 18)***: Article 18 of the Indian Constitution's deals with the abolition titles. It is restricted the state from bestowing any title on any person, whether a citizen or a foreigner, with the exception of military or scholarly accomplishments. Also forbids Indian nationals from taking up titles from any other country. Under the article provision the use of inherited titles of nobility, such as Maharaja, Deewan, etc., that were granted by colonial nations are restricted. But does not prohibit national awards like the Bharat Ratna, Padma Vibhushan, Padma Bhushan, and Padma Sri, etc.

Significance of right to equality in Indian Constitution

Fundamental rights denote the foundational pillar for citizen of India for the development of better future prospect. The following listed below are the significance of fundamental rights (NEXT IAS Contributors, 2025)

- The words fundamental means the importance rights and overall development of the Indian citizens
- The Indian Constitution gave separated list of articles for the protection of individuals.
- Violation of Indian constitution is strictly prohibited.
- Fundamental rights cooperate the Rule of Law.

- Every citizen of India is treated equally under the law. And everyone who is an Indian citizen is entitled to freedom of movement, assembly, association, and religion, etc.
- The idea of the rule of law given by Dicey, which originated primarily in England is incorporated in Indian Constitution
- A fundamental right can only be changed by constitutional amendment. Example the Constitution (Forty-Fourth Amendment) Act, 1978, deleted the right to property and inserted in Article 300 A of the Constitution as a legal right.
- The prohibit the state from intervening in citizens' personal lives like the rights to equality, freedom of speech, freedom of religion, and other liberties.
- Fundamental rights deals with the right to education, the right to equal chances, the right to special treatment for underprivileged groups, etc.
- Fundamental Rights safeguard minority communities' freedom to exercise and maintain their language, culture, and religion and protect them from prejudice, discrimination, and oppression.
- The core concern of fundamental rights in India is Justice and Fairness. It guarantees that everyone is treated equally under the law, regardless of their economic situation, caste, background, color, religion, or gender.
- Discrimination in all areas of life, including as public services, housing, work, and education is prohibited and non-discrimination is encouraged.
- fundamental rights are the main actor for social cohesiveness it lowering tension, inequalities, untouchability and promote togetherness and sense of belongingness.
- Fundamental rights protect citizens against state arbitrary activities.
- Social Justice is encouraging and it gives the government to enact affirmative action laws, which alleviate structural injustices that underprivileged communities must deal with.
- It promotes the ideas of all people are same in law and encourage rule of law
- Fundamental rights strengthen democracy and promote a society which everyone respect each other dignity.

Important Landmark Cases

Different fundamental rights related cases are affirmed by the Supreme Court. The following are significant landmark cases pertaining to the Articles 14–18, Right to Equality (Pahuja Law Academy, n.d; Agrawal, 2024).

- ***In E.P. Royappa v. State of Tamil Nadu (1974)***: The Supreme Court declared that equality and arbitrariness are sworn rivals, expanding the application of Article 14. "Equality is a dynamic concept with many aspects and dimensions, and it cannot be cribbed, cabined and confined within traditional and doctrinaire limits." The necessity of determining whether state behavior is discriminatory or arbitrary was highlighted by this case.
- ***Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India (1978)***: By connecting Article 14 to Article 21 (right to life and personal liberty), this case considerably broadened its application. The court upheld the non-arbitrariness principle by ruling that any legislation impacting individual liberty must be reasonable, fair, and just.
- ***Kesavananda Bharati v. State of Kerala (1973)***: This case addressed Article 14 and the idea of equality before the law; however, it is most recognized for its basic structural theory. The ruling stressed that legislation shouldn't arbitrarily discriminate against people and should instead be just, fair, and reasonable.
- ***The historic case of Indra Sawhney v. Union of India (1992)***: Addressed reservations for Other Backward Classes (OBCs) in public employment. The Supreme Court emphasized that caste cannot be the only factor used to determine backwardness while upholding the legitimacy of reservations.
- ***Mc Mehta v. State of Tamil Nadu (1996)***: This case dealt with environmental pollution brought on by Tamil Nadu's industries. The Supreme Court put strict controls on businesses that violate environmental standards after ruling that the right to a clean environment is a component of the right to life under Article 21.
- ***State of Kerala v. N.M. Thomas (1976)***: Article 15(4), which permits the State to make specific arrangements for the improvement of socially and educationally backward sections, Reservations should strive for real social advancement without sustaining casteism, the Supreme Court stressed.
- ***M. Nagaraj v. Union of India (2006)***: The constitutionality of reservations in promotions for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes under Article 16(4) was examined in The Supreme Court stressed that reservations in promotions shouldn't go over the 50% ceiling while upholding the legitimacy of creamy layer exclusion.
- ***State of Karnataka v. Appa Balu Ingale***: The 1993 case addressed the practice of untouchability and the application of Article 17 regulations that prohibited it. The Supreme Court reiterated its commitment to protecting disadvantaged groups and ending untouchability.
- ***R. Veeraswamy v. Tamil Nadu Electricity Board (1999)***: The application of a new pension plan to workers who had retired prior to the plan's launch was at issue in this case. The Supreme Court was

requested to rule on whether pensioners might claim benefits under the new plan if they had already received their retirement payments.

Suggestion

1. Public campaigns and education to all citizen are the organ to raise awareness of fundamental rights to make sure people understand their rights and how important it is to protect them.
2. To organise proper legal awareness programme in village level, district levels and state level for fundamental rights.
3. Government, law enforcement, and the courts should defend and maintain fundamental rights in order to strengthen their implementation.
4. Streamlining legal activities and organise legal aid programme specially for the disadvantages section and economic backwards groups to access the fair justice
5. Amendment, review, update and reform of Fundamental Rights are required.
6. The people should understand that exercising their rights shouldn't hurt society as a whole or violate the rights of others.
7. Respect women, children, LGBTQ+ people, religious minorities, and indigenous communities and to protect vulnerable groups.

Conclusion

When the Indian constitution was adopted, there was originally seven fundamental rights. However, the Right to Property (Article 31) was eliminated by the 44th Constitutional Amendment in 1978 and added in art. 300A. The right to equality Articles 14–18 in Indian Constitutions is core foundation for the development of fair and equal society.

Reference

Vajiram Editor. (2026, January 2). *Fundamental rights – Articles 12 to 35 of the Indian Constitution*.

Vajiram & Ravi. Retrieved from <https://vajiramandravi.com/upsc-exam/fundamental-rights/>. Accessed on January 15, 2026.

NEXT IAS Contributors. (2025, October 24). *Right to equality (Article 14 to 18): Meaning, provisions & significance*. Next IAS. Retrieved from <https://www.nextias.com/blog/right-to-equality/>. Accessed on January 15, 2026.

Khaskalam, Y. (2025, February 3). *Articles 14–18 of the Indian Constitution: Equality and its implications*. Government of India. Retrieved from <https://education.vikaspedia.in/viewcontent/education/law-and-constitution/fundamental-rights-article-14-35/articles-14-18-of-the-indian-constitution-equality-and-its-implications?lgn=en>. Accessed on January 15, 2026.

Pahuja Law Academy. (n.d.). *Fundamental rights and landmark constitutional cases*. Retrieved from <https://www.pahujalawacademy.com/fundamental-rights-and-landmark-constitutional-cases>. Accessed on January 15, 2026.

Agrawal, A. (2024, December 27). *Article 14 of the Indian Constitution*. Law Bhoomi. Retrieved from <https://lawbhoomi.com/article-14-of-indian-constitution/>. Accessed on January 15, 2026.

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